

Correspondence Principle and x-Derivative of Information

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The quantum free particle form $\exp(ipx)$, together with the momentum operator $-i\hbar/dx$, maps to classical physics through $-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = p$ and $-i\hbar/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = pp$. In other words, p multiplied by p yields pp . In the case of a bound system with a potential $V(x)$, one might suggest creating a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, where $W(x)$ is called a wavefunction.

In this note, we do not form the linear combination $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but rather postulate a function $W(x)$ which replaces $\exp(ipx)$ in a bound situation. We try to use strictly classical reasoning to find a relationship between $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle pp \rangle$ which in the high energy limit for a bound state yields the classical result $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle = \langle pp \rangle$. Here there exists a probability distribution function which may be used to calculate $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle pp \rangle$. We try to argue that the form $\langle p(x) \rangle = -i\hbar/dx W$ and $\langle pp \rangle(x) = -i\hbar/dx d/dx W/W$ follow from these ideas. In particular, we argue that the probability distribution becomes a hat function in a tiny region defined by $1/\langle p(x) \rangle$.

P time p = pp in Classical Mechanics and For Quantum Free Particles

In classical mechanics, one considers tiny dx and dt intervals and essentially has points in space and time. Thus, $p(x,t)$ is a number and $p(x,t)$ times $p(x,t)$ is its square and is used in a nonrelativistic expression for kinetic energy, $pp/2m$.

Interestingly, a quantum free particle also has this relationship as is well known. Given the free particle wavefunction proportional to $\exp(ipx)$:

$$\langle p \rangle = -i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \langle pp \rangle = -i\hbar/dx d/dx \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx) \quad ((1b))$$

Thus: $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle = \langle pp \rangle$ for a quantum free particle.

If one considers a bound state with a potential $V(x)$, however, one does not expect $\exp(ipx)$ to apply.

Quantum Bound State and the Correspondence Principle

We suggest $\exp(ipx)$ in a bound system is replaced by a function $W(x)$ (real because forward and backwards motion are included together with equal magnitude weights). One might postulate using $W(x) = \text{Sum over } a(p) \exp(ipx)$, but we do not use this postulate. We suggest that:

$$\langle p(x) \rangle \langle p(x) \rangle \neq \langle pp \rangle(x) \quad ((3))$$

((3)), however, directly contradicts classical mechanics. If one considers the correspondence principle, then in the high energy limit, one should have equality in ((3)). We suggest that this yields insight into the quantum bound situation.

The main idea that we use is that the probability distribution used to calculate $\langle p(x) \rangle$ has a natural base length. In other words, there is no dx shrinking to zero as in Newtonian mechanics. One has a space rather broken into chunks, which as of yet have unknown length. In the high energy limit, we suggest that that probability function becomes sharp, i.e. defines almost Newtonian dx regions. In such a case, the probability distribution has a very sharp slope. We suggest that is like a hat function (two step functions), so that within the base x region of the distribution, $d/dx \langle p(x) \rangle = 0$.

We suggest that in general

$$\langle p(x) \rangle \langle p(x+b(x)) \rangle = \langle pp \rangle (x) \quad ((4))$$

with $b(x)$ being completely unknown, but within the small region of the probability distribution chunk. Furthermore, $b(x)$ must approach 0 in the high energy limit due to the correspondence principle. For the case of a small $b(x)$, we expand:

$$\langle p(x) \rangle \langle p(x) \rangle + \langle p(x) \rangle b(x) \frac{d}{dx} \langle p(x) \rangle = \langle pp \rangle (x) \quad ((5))$$

Even though $b(x)$ is small, $p(x)$ may become large because one is approaching a high n limit. As noted, in the high energy limit, the probability becomes a hat function and $d/dx \langle p \rangle = 0$. In order, that the second term on the LHS of ((5)) not be large, one suggests that:

$$\langle p(x) \rangle b(x) = \text{Order}(1) \rightarrow b(x) \approx 1/\langle p(x) \rangle \quad ((6))$$

((6)) need not only hold in the high n limit, but may actually be quantum property with $b(x)$ defining a "small" length in quantum mechanics which is actually not defined from "outside" as in Newtonian mechanics, but from $\langle p(x) \rangle$. In such a case, ((5)) may hold in general with $b(x) = C/\langle p(x) \rangle$, C being an unknown constant.

One now has the notion of information as:

$$1/\langle p(x) \rangle \frac{d}{dx} \langle p(x) \rangle = \frac{d}{dx} \ln(\langle p(x) \rangle) \quad ((7))$$

We next ask: Is it possible to use ((5)) to deduce a closer link between $\langle p(x) \rangle$ and $\langle pp \rangle (x)$?

We argue that ((5)) seems to be similar to the product rule for derivatives, but note that $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle$ and $\langle pp \rangle$ are on opposite sides of the equal sign. This suggests a derivative product rule which introduces a minus sign. This implies a function W with a derivative in the numerator and a W in the denominator, e.g.

$dW/dx / W$ (which is directly linked to information if $W(x)$ is a probability).

In other words, one tries to link p to a derivative in dW/dx i.e.

$$d/dx (dW/dx / W) = d/dx dW/dx / W - dW/dx dW/dx / WW \quad ((8))$$

This suggests that $\langle p(x) \rangle = dW/dx / W$ constant and $\langle pp \rangle(x) = \text{constant}^2 \quad d/dx dW/dx / W \quad ((9))$

This is in keeping with the free particle form $\exp(ipx)$.

Thus, we argue that classical type arguments together with the correspondence principle lead to the form $\langle p(x) \rangle = \text{constant} \quad dW/dx / W$ which is of the form of an x-derivative of information and the quantum mechanical result. This, we argue, is derived without use of the free particle form $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, the quantum mechanical form seems to follow strictly from classical arguments and the idea of a distribution within a base chunk which becomes a hat function in the high energy limit.

Conclusion

Quantum mechanics usually introduces momentum in terms of an operator $-i\hbar/dx$ acting on a function $W(x)$, called a wavefunction. This begs the question: How does $-i\hbar/dx$ emerge? In addition, a free particle wavefunction is then introduced as $\exp(ipx)$. In the case of a bound single particle system in a potential $V(x)$, it is suggested that $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ be used, i.e. a superposition or sum of OR probabilities using an unusual $\exp(ipx)$ dynamic sort of probability.

Here, we try to find the form $\langle p(x) \rangle = dW/dx / W$ constant for a bound system using only classical ideas and the correspondence principle. We do not introduce $-i\hbar/dx$ a priori as the momentum operator and do not need to know about $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that unlike Newtonian mechanics where changes in $p(x)$ occur in a dx which tends to 0, there exists a distribution function which describes a small region. This region must be defined, but it defines itself in a certain sense as we argue. We suggest that in the case of distribution within a tiny region, $\langle p(x) \rangle \langle p(x) \rangle \neq \langle pp \rangle(x)$. We further suggest that one use: $\langle p(x) \rangle \langle p(x+b(x)) \rangle = \langle pp \rangle(x)$. If $b(x)$ is considered to be a correction within the tiny interval, one may expand using a Taylor series. This suggests that: $p(x) b(x) d\langle p(x) \rangle / dx$ tends to zero in the high energy limit due to the correspondence principle. Given that $p(x)$ may become large in the high energy limit, it should be offset by $b(x)$, so we suggest that $b(x)$ is proportional to $1/p(x)$. Within the tiny region governed by the probability distribution, we suggest that as energy becomes very high, this becomes a hat function. Then $d/dx \langle p(x) \rangle = 0$ in this region and $\langle p(x) \rangle \langle p(x) \rangle = \langle pp \rangle(x)$. We suggest that the form: $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle + d/dx \langle p(x) \rangle = \langle pp \rangle(x)$ maps into a derivative of quotients form, if one uses $\langle p \rangle = dW/dx / W$ constant¹. Then $\langle pp \rangle$ becomes $d/dx dW/dx / W$. In other words, we try to obtain the quantum form $dW/dx / W$ using only classical ideas and the notion of a probability distribution in a tiny region of space.. The tiny region $b(x)$ is defined by $1/\langle p(x) \rangle$ and so W which defines $\langle p \rangle$ also defines $1/\langle p \rangle$. We note that this approach also yields the free particle result.

